

CLOSED-FORM EXPRESSIONS FOR SERIES INVOLVING THE DERIVATIVES OF THE HURWITZ AND LERCH ZETA FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we derive closed-form expressions for series involving derivatives of the Hurwitz zeta function and Stirling numbers of the first kind in terms of the Hurwitz zeta function, Bell polynomials, and the generalized Stieltjes constants. These results extend classical rational zeta series evaluations and yield new representation of the generalized Stieltjes constants. Our approach is based on the power series and Fourier series expansions of the Hurwitz zeta function with respect to its last variable. We also obtain analogous results for series involving derivatives of the Lerch zeta function and Stirling numbers of the first kind in terms of the Lerch zeta function and Bell polynomials.

1. INTRODUCTION

For $\Re(s) > 1$ and $\Re(a) > 0$, the Hurwitz and Lerch zeta function are defined by

$$\zeta(s, a) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+a)^s}, \quad L(\lambda, s, a) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{2\pi i k \lambda}}{(k+a)^s}. \quad (1.1)$$

If $\lambda \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}$, then the Lerch zeta function converges also for $\Re(s) > 0$. In particular, when $\lambda \in \mathbb{Z}$, then $L(\lambda, s, a) = \zeta(s, a)$.

It is known that the Hurwitz zeta function and the Lerch zeta function have the functional equations [19], [3]:

$$\zeta(1-s, a) = 2(2\pi)^{-s} \Gamma(s) \left\{ \cos \frac{\pi}{2} s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2\pi k a}{k^s} + \sin \frac{\pi}{2} s \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin 2\pi k a}{k^s} \right\}, \quad (1.2)$$

where $\Gamma(s)$ is the gamma function and

$$\begin{aligned} L(\lambda, 1-s, a) \\ = (2\pi)^{-s} \Gamma(s) \left\{ e^{\pi i (\frac{s}{2} - 2a\lambda)} L(-a, s, \lambda) + e^{\pi i (-\frac{s}{2} + 2a(1-\lambda))} L(a, s, 1-\lambda) \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

for $\Re(s) > 1$ and $0 < a < 1$. Consequently, these two functions can be analytically continued to $\mathbb{C} \setminus \{1\}$ and \mathbb{C} respectively.

The derivatives of the Hurwitz zeta function with respect to s are given by

$$\zeta^{(r)}(s, a) = \frac{\partial^r}{\partial s^r} \zeta(s, a) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+a)^s} (-\log(k+a))^r,$$

and similarly for $L^{(r)}(\lambda, s, a)$.

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The generalized Stieltjes constants $\gamma_k(a)$ are defined by the Laurent series expansion at $s = 1$ of the Hurwitz zeta function,

$$\zeta(s, a) = \frac{1}{s-1} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k (s-1)^k}{k!} \gamma_k(a). \quad (1.4)$$

Especially, $\gamma_k = \gamma_k(1)$ denotes the ordinary Stieltjes constant.

Note that for $k = 0$, the generalized Stieltjes constant satisfies

$$\gamma_0(a) = -\psi(a),$$

where $\psi(s) = \frac{d}{ds} \log \Gamma(s)$ denotes the digamma function (see [9]).

Several representations of the generalized Stieltjes constants are known. A classical limit representation due to Berndt [7] is

$$\gamma_r(a) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \sum_{j=0}^m \frac{\log^r(j+a)}{j+a} - \frac{\log^{r+1}(m+a)}{r+1} \right\}. \quad (1.5)$$

Moreover, Coffey obtained the following series representation for $\Re(a) > 0$ and $|x| < |a|$, [11]:

$$\gamma_r(a-x) = \gamma_r(a) + (-1)^r \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^{k-1}}{(k-1)!} \sum_{l=0}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l+1 \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k, a), \quad (1.6)$$

where $\begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix}$ is the Stirling numbers of the first kind, that is, [1]

$$x(x+1) \cdots (x+k-1) = \sum_{l=0}^k \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} x^l. \quad (1.7)$$

Prévost obtained a new representation for γ_1 [16]:

$$\gamma_1 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(2k+1)}{2k+1}.$$

In this paper, we derive closed-form expressions for the following series, which are related to (1.6):

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k, a) \quad (1.8)$$

and

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a) \quad (1.9)$$

for $d \in \mathbb{N}$. Note that if $r = 1$, then (1.8) is

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(k, a)}{k(k+d)} x^k,$$

which has been studied by several authors [13], [18], [15], and [2]. While several authors have obtained closed-form expressions for series involving the Hurwitz zeta function itself, considerably less is known for series involving higher order derivatives of the Hurwitz and Lerch zeta function. The formulas obtained in this paper may therefore be regarded as higher-order analogues and extensions of these earlier results.

The closed-forms of (1.8) and (1.9) involve the Lerch zeta function, generalized Stieltjes constants, and complete Bell polynomials. The complete Bell polynomials $Y_n(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ are defined by [6]

$$Y_n(x_1, \dots, x_n) = n! \sum_{j_1+2j_2+\dots+nj_n=n} \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^{j_i}}{(i!)^{j_i} j_i!}. \quad (1.10)$$

With this definition, we obtain the generating series

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{Y_n(x_1, \dots, x_n)}{n!} z^n = \exp\left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{x_j}{j!} z^j\right). \quad (1.11)$$

Note that the Stirling numbers of the first kind can be represented by the complete Bell polynomials, that is, for $k, l \in \mathbb{N}$, [12, p. 217]

$$\begin{bmatrix} k \\ l+1 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{(k-1)!}{l!} Y_l(H_{k-1}, \dots, (-1)^{l-1} (l-1)! H_{k-1}^{(l)}) \quad (1.12)$$

where

$$H_k = \sum_{r=1}^k \frac{1}{r} \quad \text{and} \quad H_k^{(m)} = \sum_{r=1}^k \frac{1}{r^m}.$$

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we prove the main theorems giving closed-form expressions for series involving the derivatives of the Hurwitz and Lerch zeta function and the Stirling numbers of the first kind. The proofs combine Taylor series and Fourier series of zeta functions with respect to their last variable. In Section 3, we derive several evaluations of these series and establish new series representations for the generalized Stieltjes constants.

2. MAIN RESULT

Theorem 2.1. *For $r, d \in \mathbb{N}$, $a \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\Re(a) > 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{C}$ satisfying $0 < |x| \leq |a|$,*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k, a) \\ &= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{1}{x^n} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} \zeta^{(r-m)}(-n, a-x) Y_m(H_n, \dots, (m-1)! H_n^{(m)}) \\ &+ \frac{1}{dx^d} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} \zeta^{(r-m)}(-d, a) Y_m(H_d, \dots, (m-1)! H_d^{(m)}) \\ &- \frac{1}{d} \zeta^{(r)}(0, a) - \frac{(-1)^{r-1} r x}{d+1} \gamma_{r-1}(a). \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

Moreover, for $0 < \lambda < 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a) \\
&= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{1}{x^n} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} L^{(r-m)}(\lambda, -n, a-x) Y_m(H_n, \dots, (m-1)!H_n^{(m)}) \\
&+ \frac{1}{dx^d} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} L^{(r-m)}(\lambda, -d, a) Y_m(H_d, \dots, (m-1)!H_d^{(m)}) \\
&- \frac{1}{d} L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a) - \frac{rx}{d+1} L^{(r-1)}(\lambda, 1, a).
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Remark 1. From $\zeta(s, a) = \zeta(s, a+1) + a^{-s}$, differentiating r times with respect to s and then setting $s = -n$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ yields $\zeta^{(r)}(-n, a) = \zeta^{(r)}(-n, a+1) + (-1)^r a^n \log^r a$. Hence, as $a \rightarrow 0^+$, we define $\zeta^{(r)}(-n, 0) = \zeta^{(r)}(-n)$. Similarly, since $L(\lambda, s, a) = e^{2\pi i \lambda} L(\lambda, s, a+1) + a^{-s}$, we define $L^{(r)}(\lambda, -n, 0) = e^{2\pi i \lambda} L^{(r)}(\lambda, -n, 1)$.

Example 2.1. Using the well known formula

$$\zeta'(0, a) = \log \Gamma(a) - \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi$$

(see [8]), then for $r = 1$, (2.1) is

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(k, a)}{k(k+d)} x^k &= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{\zeta'(-n, a-x) + \zeta(-n, a-x) H_n}{x^n} \\
&+ \frac{\zeta'(-d, a) + \zeta(-d, a) H_d}{dx^d} - \frac{1}{d} \left(\log \Gamma(a) - \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi \right) + \frac{x}{d+1} \psi(a).
\end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

Example 2.2. If $r = 2$, then (2.1) is

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2 \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(k, a) + \zeta(k, a) H_{k-1}}{k(k+d)} x^k \\
&= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{\zeta''(-n, a-x) + 2\zeta'(-n, a-x) H_n + \zeta(-n, a-x) (H_n^2 + H_n^{(2)})}{x^n} \\
&+ \frac{\zeta''(-d, a) + 2\zeta'(-d, a) H_d + \zeta(-d, a) (H_d^2 + H_d^{(2)})}{dx^d} \\
&- \frac{1}{d} \zeta''(0, a) + \frac{2x}{d+1} \gamma_1(a).
\end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

Proof. The proof combines a local Taylor expansion (Proposition 2.2) with a Fourier expansion for derivatives of the Hurwitz and the Lerch zeta function (Proposition 2.3). Comparing two evaluations of the same integral yields Theorem 2.1.

Proposition 2.2. For $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $a \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\Re(a) > 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{C}$ satisfying $0 < |x| < |a|$,

$$\zeta^{(r)}(0, a-x) = \zeta^{(r)}(0, a) + (-1)^{r-1} r \gamma_{r-1}(a) x + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k, a). \tag{2.5}$$

Moreover, for $0 < \lambda < 1$,

$$L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a - x) = L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a). \quad (2.6)$$

Proof. Suppose

$$f(x) = L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a - x)$$

For $k \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\frac{\partial^k}{\partial x^k} L(\lambda, s, a - x) = g_k(s) L(\lambda, s + k, a - x) \quad (2.7)$$

where $g_k(s) = s \cdots (s + k - 1)$. Differentiating (2.7) r times with respect to s , we obtain

$$\frac{\partial^k}{\partial x^k} L^{(r)}(\lambda, s, a - x) = \sum_{l=0}^r \binom{r}{l} g_k^{(l)}(s) L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, s + k, a - x). \quad (2.8)$$

Since

$$g_k(s) = \sum_{j=0}^k \begin{bmatrix} k \\ j \end{bmatrix} s^j,$$

we have

$$g_k(0) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad g_k^{(l)}(0) = l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \text{ for } k \geq 1.$$

Taking the limit as $s \rightarrow 0$ in (2.8), we get

$$f^{(k)}(x) = \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a - x). \quad (2.9)$$

Applying Taylor's theorem at $x = 0$, we get (2.6). Finally, to prove that (2.6) converges absolutely for $|x| < |a|$, note that by (1.10) and (1.12),

$$\begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} = \frac{(k-1)!}{(l-1)!} Y_{l-1}(H_{k-1}, \dots, (-1)^{l-2} (l-2)! H_{k-1}^{(l-1)}) = O_l((k-1)! \log^{l-1} k)$$

and for fixed n, λ , and $\Re(a) > 0$,

$$L^{(n)}(\lambda, k, a) = O_{n,\lambda,a}(|a|^{-k})$$

as $k \rightarrow \infty$, where $O(\cdot)$ is the big O notation. Hence, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{x^k}{k!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a) \right| &\leq \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{x^k}{k!} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a) \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! C_{l,r,\lambda,a} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\log^{l-1} k}{k} \left| \frac{x}{a} \right|^k \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where $C_{l,r,\lambda,a}$ is a constant independent of k . Since the (RHS) of (2.10) converges for $|x| < |a|$, (2.6) converges absolutely for $|x| < |a|$.

In a similar way, we obtain (2.5), but since $\zeta^{(r)}(s, a)$ has a pole at $s = 1$, the argument used above requires a separate treatment when $k = 1$. In this case, the first derivative of the $\zeta^{(r)}(0, a - x)$ is given by

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left(s \zeta^{(r)}(s + 1, a - x) + r \zeta^{(r-1)}(s + 1, a - x) \right)$$

By (1.4),

$$\begin{aligned} & s\zeta^{(r)}(s+1, z) + r\zeta^{(r-1)}(s+1, z) \\ &= (-1)^r \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k s^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} (k+r+1)\gamma_{k+r}(z) - r\gamma_{r-1}(z) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Taking the limit as $s \rightarrow 0$, we obtain

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left(s\zeta^{(r)}(s+1, a-x) + r\zeta^{(r-1)}(s+1, a-x) \right) = (-1)^{r-1} r\gamma_{r-1}(a-x)$$

Applying Taylor's theorem at $x = 0$ therefore yields (2.5). \square

The next proposition is based on the Fourier series of the Lerch zeta function.

Proposition 2.3. *For $s \neq 0, -1, -2, \dots$ and $z \neq 0$, define*

$$\bar{Y}_r(s, z) = Y_r(-\psi(s) + \log(2\pi z), \zeta(2, s), \dots, (r-1)!\zeta(r, s)).$$

Then for $r \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $\omega \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\Re(\omega) > 0$, and $0 < x < 1$,

$$\zeta^{(r)}(1-\omega, x) = \Gamma(\omega) \sum_{k=-\infty, k \neq 0}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(\omega, ik)}{(2\pi ik)^\omega} e^{2\pi ikx}. \quad (2.11)$$

Moreover, for $0 < \lambda < 1$,

$$L^{(r)}(\lambda, 1-\omega, x) = \Gamma(\omega) \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(\omega, i(k-\lambda))}{(2\pi i(k-\lambda))^\omega} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)x}. \quad (2.12)$$

Furthermore, both series above converge uniformly on $[\delta, 1-\delta]$ for every $0 < \delta < \frac{1}{2}$.

Remark 2. For $r = 0$, (2.12) was obtained by Navas, Ruiz, and Varona [14]. Furthermore, Rane derived the Fourier series for the Hurwitz zeta function and its derivatives [17].

Proof. For $r \geq 0$, define

$$a_r(k) = \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i\lambda x} L^{(r)}(\lambda, 1-\omega, x) e^{-2\pi ikx} dx.$$

Since $L(\lambda, s, x)$ is entire with respect to s , the Taylor series

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^n}{n!} L^{(n)}(\lambda, s, x) = L(\lambda, t+s, x)$$

converges uniformly on any closed disk $\{t : |t| \leq R\}$. Hence by interchanging summation and integration, we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^n}{n!} a_n(k) = \int_0^1 L(\lambda, t+1-\omega, x) e^{-2\pi i(k-\lambda)x} dx \quad (2.13)$$

for some small t . And for $0 < t < 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 L(\lambda, t, x) e^{-2\pi i(k-\lambda)x} dx &= \int_0^1 \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{2\pi i j \lambda}}{(j+x)^t} e^{-2\pi i(k-\lambda)x} dx + \int_0^1 x^{-t} e^{-2\pi i(k-\lambda)x} dx \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \int_j^{j+1} x^{-t} e^{-2\pi i(k-\lambda)x} dx \\ &= \Gamma(1-t)(2\pi i(k-\lambda))^{t-1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

Interchanging summation and integration is justified by Dirichlet's test, since the partial sums of $e^{2\pi i j \lambda}$ are uniformly bounded and $(j+x)^{-t}$ decreases monotonically to 0 as $j \rightarrow \infty$ and $x \in [0, 1]$. By identity theorem, (2.14) can be extended to $\Re(t) < 1$.

Since the Taylor series [10]

$$\log \Gamma(s-t) = \log \Gamma(s) - \psi(s)t + \sum_{j=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(j, s)}{j} t^j$$

holds for t in a sufficiently small neighborhood of 0, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^n}{n!} \bar{Y}_n(s, z) &= \exp \left(\sum_{j=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(j, s)}{j} t^j + \{ -\psi(s) + \log(2\pi z) \} t \right) \\ &= \exp \left(\log \Gamma(s-t) - \log \Gamma(s) + t \log(2\pi z) \right) \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(s-t)}{\Gamma(s)} (2\pi z)^t. \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

So by using (2.13), (2.14) and (2.15),

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^n}{n!} a_n(k) &= \frac{\Gamma(\omega)}{(2\pi i(k-\lambda))^\omega} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^n}{n!} \bar{Y}_n(\omega, i(k-\lambda)). \\ \therefore a_r(k) &= \frac{\Gamma(\omega)}{(2\pi i(k-\lambda))^\omega} \bar{Y}_r(\omega, i(k-\lambda)) \end{aligned}$$

Finally, to establish the uniform convergence of the Fourier series in (2.12), it suffices to show that the series

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\log^r(k-\lambda)}{(k-\lambda)^{\Re(\omega)}} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)x} \quad (2.16)$$

converges uniformly on $[\delta, 1-\delta]$ for every $0 < \delta < \frac{1}{2}$ since $\bar{Y}_r(\omega, i(k-\lambda)) = O_{r,\omega,\lambda}(\log^r |k-\lambda|)$ by (1.10) implies

$$\left| \frac{\bar{Y}_r(\omega, i(k-\lambda))}{(2\pi i(k-\lambda))^\omega} \right| \leq C_{r,\omega,\lambda} \frac{\log^r |k-\lambda|}{|k-\lambda|^{\Re(\omega)}}$$

where $C_{r,\omega,\lambda}$ is a constant independent of k and by dividing the sum for $k \geq 1$ and $k \leq 0$ and, replacing $k \mapsto -k$ for negative part, we obtain a similar form of (2.16). If we define

$$c_k = \frac{\log^r(k-\lambda)}{(k-\lambda)^{\Re(\omega)}},$$

then $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} c_k = 0$ and c_k is eventually monotone decreasing. Since for $x \in [\delta, 1 - \delta]$,

$$\left| \sum_{k=k_0}^N e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)x} \right| \leq \frac{1}{|\sin \pi x|} \leq \frac{1}{\sin \pi \delta},$$

(2.16) converges uniformly on $[\delta, 1 - \delta]$ by Dirichlet test. Since the Fourier coefficients of the uniformly convergent series coincide with the Fourier coefficients of $L^{(r)}(\lambda, 1 - \omega, x)$, uniqueness of Fourier series implies that (2.12) holds for $0 < x < 1$.

To find the Fourier series of $\zeta^{(r)}(1 - \omega, x)$, we will use the series expansion of the Lerch zeta function [5, p. 30] for $s \neq 1, 2, \dots$ and $0 < \lambda < 1$,

$$e^{2\pi i \lambda x} L(\lambda, s, x) = \Gamma(1 - s)(-2\pi i \lambda)^{s-1} + \zeta(s, x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(s - n, x)}{n!} (2\pi i \lambda)^n. \quad (2.17)$$

Since by (2.15),

$$\Gamma(1 - s)(-2\pi i \lambda)^{s-1} = \frac{\Gamma(\omega)}{(-2\pi i \lambda)^\omega} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(s + \omega - 1)^k}{k!} \bar{Y}_k(\omega, -i\lambda),$$

by differentiating r times with respect to s , substituting $s = 1 - \omega$, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial^r}{\partial s^r} \{ \Gamma(1 - s)(-2\pi i \lambda)^{s-1} \}_{s=1-\omega} = \frac{\Gamma(\omega)}{(-2\pi i \lambda)^\omega} \bar{Y}_r(\omega, -i\lambda),$$

So by differentiating (2.17) r times with respect to s , substituting $s = 1 - \omega$, and combining (2.12), we obtain

$$e^{2\pi i \lambda x} \Gamma(\omega) \sum_{k=-\infty, k \neq 0}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(\omega, i(k - \lambda))}{(2\pi i(k - \lambda))^\omega} e^{2\pi i(k - \lambda)x} = \zeta^{(r)}(1 - \omega, x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta^{(r)}(1 - \omega - n, x)}{n!} (2\pi i \lambda)^n. \quad (2.18)$$

The series on the right-hand side of (2.18) is locally uniformly convergent for sufficiently small λ . Moreover, arguing as above, one sees that the series on the left-hand side of (2.18) converges uniformly on $\lambda \in (-\lambda_0, \lambda_0)$ for fixed x and every $0 < \lambda_0 < \frac{1}{2}$. Hence, as $\lambda \rightarrow 0$, we obtain (2.11). \square

proof of Theorem 2.1. we first prove (1.9) for $0 < x < a \leq 1$. By (2.6),

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^x t^{d-1} L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a - t) dt \\ &= L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a) \int_0^x t^{d-1} dt + \int_0^x \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{t^{k+d-1}}{k!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a) dt \\ &= L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a) \frac{x^d}{d} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{k+d}}{k!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a). \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

And since

$$Y_r(x_1 + y_1, \dots, x_r + y_r) = \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} Y_{r-m}(x_1, \dots, x_r) Y_m(y_1, \dots, y_r)$$

and for $c \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\psi(c+1) - H_c = \psi(1) \quad \zeta(j, c+1) + H_c^{(j)} = \zeta(j),$$

by using (2.12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(1, i(k-\lambda))}{(k-\lambda)^{c+1}} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)(a-x)} \\
 &= \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)(a-x)}}{(k-\lambda)^{c+1}} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} \bar{Y}_{r-m}(c+1, i(k-\lambda)) Y_m(H_c, \dots, (m-1)! H_c^{(m)}) \\
 &= \frac{(2\pi i)^{c+1}}{c!} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} L^{(r-m)}(\lambda, -c, a-x) Y_m(H_c, \dots, (m-1)! H_c^{(m)}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_0^x t^{d-1} L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a-t) dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_0^x t^{d-1} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(1, i(k-\lambda))}{k-\lambda} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)(a-t)} dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(1, i(k-\lambda))}{k-\lambda} \int_0^x t^{d-1} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)(a-t)} dt \\
 &= -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(1, i(k-\lambda))}{k-\lambda} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)(a-x)} \sum_{n=1}^d \frac{x^{d-n}}{(2\pi i(k-\lambda))^n} \frac{(d-1)!}{(d-n)!} \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(1, i(k-\lambda))}{k-\lambda} \frac{(d-1)!}{(2\pi i(k-\lambda))^d} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)a} \\
 &= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{n! x^{d-n}}{(2\pi i)^{n+1}} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(1, i(k-\lambda))}{(k-\lambda)^{n+1}} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)(a-x)} \\
 &+ \frac{(d-1)!}{(2\pi i)^{d+1}} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\bar{Y}_r(1, i(k-\lambda))}{(k-\lambda)^{d+1}} e^{2\pi i(k-\lambda)a} \\
 &= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} x^{d-n} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} L^{(r-m)}(\lambda, -n, a-x) Y_m(H_n, \dots, (m-1)! H_n^{(m)}) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{d} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} L^{(r-m)}(\lambda, -d, a) Y_m(H_d, \dots, (m-1)! H_d^{(m)})
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.20}$$

By comparing (2.19) and (2.20), we obtain (1.9) for $0 < x < a \leq 1$.

Next, we extend the result to the complex domain $0 < |x| < |a|$ and $\Re(a) > 0$. The key idea is to interpret both sides as holomorphic functions and apply the identity theorem successively in each variable. Let $a \in (0, 1]$ be fixed and $F(x, a)$ be the difference between the left-hand side and the right-hand side of (2.2). By

the same argument as in (2.10), we obtain

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left| \frac{x^k}{k!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a) \right| \leq C' \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\log^{l-1} k}{k(k+d)} \left| \frac{x}{a} \right|^k.$$

Since

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\log^{l-1} k}{k(k+d)} \left| \frac{x}{a} \right|^k$$

converges for $|x| \leq a$, the series in (2.2) converges uniformly for $|x| \leq a$ by Weierstrass M test, which implies that $x \mapsto F(x, a)$ is holomorphic for $0 < |x| < a$. Since $F(x, a) = 0$ for $0 < x < a$, the identity theorem yields that $F(x, a) = 0$ for $0 < |x| < a$. Now fix x with $0 < |x| < 1$. Since $F(x, a) = 0$ for all $a \in (|x|, 1)$, and $a \mapsto F(x, a)$ is holomorphic on $\{a \in \mathbb{C} : |a| > |x|\}$, another application of the identity theorem yields $F(x, a) = 0$ for $0 < |x| < |a|$. Finally, for any z with $|z| = |a|$, letting $x \rightarrow z$ from within the disk $|x| < |a|$ and using the uniform convergence of the series, we can interchange the limit and summation, which yields (2.2) on the boundary $|x| = |a|$. Similarly, we also obtain (2.1) \square

Corollary 2.4. For $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $d \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $0 < \lambda < 1$, $a \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\Re(a) > 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{C}$ satisfying $0 < |x| < |a|$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{(k-1)!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k, a) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{1}{x^n} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} \zeta^{(r-m)}(-n, a-x) Y_m(H_n, \dots, (m-1)!H_n^{(m)}) \\ & \quad - \frac{1}{x^d} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} \zeta^{(r-m)}(-d, a) Y_m(H_d, \dots, (m-1)!H_d^{(m)}) \\ & \quad + \zeta^{(r)}(0, a-x) - \frac{(-1)^{r-1} r x}{d+1} \gamma_{r-1}(a). \end{aligned} \tag{2.21}$$

Moreover, for $0 < \lambda < 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{(k-1)!(k+d)} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} L^{(r-l)}(\lambda, k, a) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{1}{x^n} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} L^{(r-m)}(\lambda, -n, a-x) Y_m(H_n, \dots, (m-1)!H_n^{(m)}) \\ & \quad - \frac{1}{x^d} \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} L^{(r-m)}(\lambda, -d, a) Y_m(H_d, \dots, (m-1)!H_d^{(m)}) \\ & \quad + L^{(r)}(\lambda, 0, a-x) - \frac{r x}{d+1} L^{(r-1)}(\lambda, 1, a) \end{aligned} \tag{2.22}$$

Proof. Since

$$\frac{1}{k+d} = \frac{1}{k} - \frac{d}{k(k+d)},$$

by using (2.1) and (2.5), we obtain (2.21). Similarly, we obtain (2.22). \square

Example 2.3. For $r = 1$, (2.21) is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(k, a)}{k+d} x^k \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{\zeta'(-n, a-x) + \zeta(-n, a-x)H_n}{x^n} - \frac{\zeta'(-d, a) + \zeta(-d, a)H_d}{x^d} \\ & \quad + \log \Gamma(a-x) + \frac{x}{d+1} \psi(a) - \frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

and for $r = 2$, (2.21) is

$$\begin{aligned} & 2 \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(k, a) + \zeta(k, a)H_{k-1}}{k+d} x^k \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{\zeta''(-n, a-x) + 2\zeta'(-n, a-x)H_n + \zeta(-n, a-x)(H_n^2 + H_n^{(2)})}{x^n} \\ & \quad - \frac{\zeta''(-d, a) + 2\zeta'(-d, a)H_d + \zeta(-d, a)(H_d^2 + H_d^{(2)})}{x^d} \\ & \quad + \zeta''(0, a-x) + \frac{2x}{d+1} \gamma_1(a). \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

3. APPLICATIONS

Example 3.1. For $a = 1$, (2.3) is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(k)}{k(k+d)} x^k &= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{\zeta'(-n, 1-x) + \zeta(-n, 1-x)H_n}{x^n} \\ & \quad + \frac{\zeta'(-d) + \zeta(-d)H_d}{dx^d} + \frac{\log 2\pi}{2d} - \frac{\gamma x}{d+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

Example 3.2. Since

$$L\left(\frac{1}{2}, s, 1\right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(n+1)^s} = (1-2^{1-s})\zeta(s), \quad L\left(\frac{1}{2}, s, \frac{1}{2}\right) = 2^s \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)^s} = 2^s \beta(s)$$

, where $\beta(s)$ are the Dirichlet beta function, for $\lambda = a = \frac{1}{2}$ and $r = 1$, (2.2) is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\beta(k)}{k(k+d)} (2x)^k &= -\frac{1}{d} \sum_{n=1}^d \binom{d}{n} \frac{L^{(1)}\left(\frac{1}{2}, -n, \frac{1}{2}-x\right) + L\left(\frac{1}{2}, -n, \frac{1}{2}-x\right)H_n}{x^n} \\ & \quad + \frac{\beta'(-d) + (\log 2 + H_d)\beta(-d)}{d(2x)^d} - \frac{\beta'(0) + \beta(0) \log 2}{d} - \frac{2\beta(1)}{d+1} x. \end{aligned}$$

For $d = 1$ and $x = \frac{1}{2}$, we obtain

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\beta(k)}{k(k+1)} = -6\zeta'(-1) + \beta'(-1) - \beta'(0) - \frac{7}{6} \log 2 - \frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{1}{2}.$$

Example 3.3. For $a = 1$ and $d = 1$, (2.4) is

$$\begin{aligned} & 2 \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(k) + \zeta(k)H_{k-1}}{k(k+1)} x^k \\ &= \frac{\zeta''(-1) - \zeta''(-1, 1-x) + 2\zeta'(-1) - 2\zeta'(-1, 1-x) + 2\zeta(-1) - 2\zeta(-1, 1-x)}{x} \\ & \quad - \zeta''(0) + \gamma_1 x. \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

Since $\zeta(s, \frac{1}{2}) = (2^s - 1)\zeta(s)$, $\zeta^{(r)}(s, \frac{3}{2}) = \zeta^{(r)}(s, \frac{1}{2}) - 2^s \log^r 2$, and $\zeta''(0) = -\frac{1}{2} \log^2 2\pi - \frac{\pi^2}{24} + \frac{1}{2}\gamma^2 + \gamma_1$ [4], we obtain for $x = \pm 1$ and $x = \pm \frac{1}{2}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(k) + \zeta(k)H_{k-1}}{k(k+1)} &= \frac{1}{4} \log^2 2\pi + \frac{\pi^2}{48} - \frac{1}{4}\gamma^2, \\ \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(k) + \zeta(k)H_{k-1}}{k(k+1)} (-1)^k &= \frac{1}{4} \log^2 2\pi + \frac{\pi^2}{48} - \frac{1}{4}\gamma^2 - \gamma_1 - 1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(k) + \zeta(k)H_{k-1}}{k(k+1)} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^k \\ &= \frac{3}{2}\zeta''(-1) + (3 - \log 2)\zeta'(-1) + \frac{1}{24} \log^2 2 + \frac{1}{4} \log^2 2\pi + \frac{1}{12} \log 2 - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{\pi^2}{48} - \frac{1}{4}\gamma^2 - \frac{1}{4}\gamma_1, \\ & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta'(k) + \zeta(k)H_{k-1}}{k(k+1)} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^k \\ &= -\frac{3}{2}\zeta''(-1) - (3 - \log 2)\zeta'(-1) - \frac{13}{24} \log^2 2 - \frac{3}{4} \log^2 2\pi - \frac{13}{12} \log 2 - 1 + \frac{\pi^2}{48} - \frac{1}{4}\gamma^2 - \frac{3}{4}\gamma_1. \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.4. Suppose $a_n = Y_n(1, \dots, (n-1)!)$. Then for $|z| < 1$, by (1.11),

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} z^n = \exp\left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(j-1)!}{j!} z^j\right) = \frac{1}{1-z} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} z^n.$$

Hence we obtain $a_n = n!$. Then for $a = 1$, $d = 1$, and $x = \pm 1$, (2.1) is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k) &= -\zeta^{(r)}(0) - \frac{(-1)^{r-1}r}{2} \gamma_{r-1}, \\ \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(k+1)!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k) &= -r! - \zeta^{(r)}(0) + \frac{(-1)^{r-1}r}{2} \gamma_{r-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\gamma_{r-1} = (-1)^{r-1}(r-1)! - \frac{2(-1)^{r-1}}{r} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+2)!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} 2k+1 \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(2k+1).$$

Example 3.5. For $a > 1$, $d = 1$, and $x = \pm 1$, (2.1) is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k, a) \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} m! [\zeta^{(r-m)}(-1, a) - \zeta^{(r-m)}(-1, a-1)] - \zeta^{(r)}(0, a) - \frac{(-1)^{r-1} r}{2} \gamma_{r-1}(a), \\ & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(k+1)!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} k \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(k, a) \\ &= - \sum_{m=0}^r \binom{r}{m} m! [\zeta^{(r-m)}(-1, a) - \zeta^{(r-m)}(-1, a+1)] - \zeta^{(r)}(0, a) + \frac{(-1)^{r-1} r}{2} \gamma_{r-1}(a). \end{aligned}$$

Hence we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{r-1}(a) &= \frac{1}{r} \sum_{m=0}^r (-1)^{m+1} \binom{r}{m} m! [a \log^{r-m} a - (a-1) \log^{r-m}(a-1)] \\ &\quad - \frac{2(-1)^{r-1}}{r} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+2)!} \sum_{l=1}^r \binom{r}{l} l! \begin{bmatrix} 2k+1 \\ l \end{bmatrix} \zeta^{(r-l)}(2k+1, a). \end{aligned}$$

Note that the convergence rate of the series improves as a increases.

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